

The Relationship between Urinary Tract Infections and Multidrug-Resistant Bacterial Pathogens Harboring Antibiotic Resistance Genes among Infected Patients in Al-Rifai City, Thi-Qar Province

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Abstract

Urinary tract infection (UTI) is one of the most prevalent bacterial infections affecting humans. It occurs when pathogenic microorganisms invade any part of the urinary system, including the kidneys, ureters, bladder, and urethra. UTIs are mainly caused by bacteria, particularly *Escherichia coli*. Other gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria can also be involved in this study aimed to investigate the relationship between urinary tract infections and multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacterial pathogens. A total of 350 urine samples were collected from males and females aged 10-75 years at Al-Rifae General Hospital in Thi-Qar province, Southern Iraq, during the period from July 2022 to January 2023. All bacterial isolates were identified using conventional biochemical tests and the VITEK-2 system, followed by confirmation using the 16S rRNA gene in addition, resistance genes were detected by PCR using bacterial colonies. Out of the 350 urine samples, 150 samples (42,9%) showed positive bacterial growth, whereas 200 samples (57,1%) were culture negative. Among 150 positive bacterial growth samples, 100 isolates were identified as multidrug-resistant (MDR). Analysis of MDR bacterial pathogens demonstrated that *E.coli* constituted the highest proportion of isolates (44%), followed by *S.aureus* (33%), *P.mirabilis* (13%), and *K.pneumoniae* (10%). Genotypic assessment revealed a high distribution of β -lactamase-encoding genes among gram-negative isolates. The blaCTX-M gene was detected in the majority of *E.coli* isolates (81,8%) and in all *K.pneumoniae* isolates, whereas a lower frequency was observed in *P.mirabilis* (30,8%). Similarly, blaSHV was identified in 29,5% of *E.coli* isolates and was universally present in *K.pneumoniae* and *P.mirabilis*. The blaAmpC gene exhibited frequencies of 90,9%, 100%, and 30,8% in *E.coli*, *K.pneumoniae*, and *P.mirabilis*, respectively. Notably, blaTEM was detected in every gram-negative isolate examined among *S.aureus* isolates, complete detection (100%) of mecA, ermA, and ermC genes was recorded.

Keywords: Resistance genes, Multiple drug resistance, UTI.

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Introduction

Urinary tract infection (UTI) is one of the most prevalent infectious diseases, caused by the invasion and multiplication of pathogenic microorganisms within the urinary tract. It is characterized by inflammatory changes that can lead to a broad spectrum of clinical manifestations, ranging from localized urinary symptoms to serious systemic complications (Flores-Mireles et al., 2015). Urinary tract infections (UTIs)

are among the most common bacterial infections and can be caused by both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria. They are classified as uncomplicated or complicated infections. The increasing prevalence of multidrug-resistant uropathogens and their virulence factors, which promote colonization, invasion, and evasion of host defenses, has become a major public health concern (Klein & Hultgren, 2020). Multidrug resistance (MDR) refers to the ability of bacteria to resist the activity of at least one antimicrobial agent from three or more different antimicrobial categories (WHO, 2024). Multidrug resistance (MDR), or multiple drug resistance, is defined as antimicrobial resistance exhibited by a microorganism to at least one agent in three or more different classes of antimicrobial drugs (Magiorakos et al., 2012). The emergence and spread of antimicrobial resistance among many human pathogens have occurred on an unprecedented scale, with resistance increasingly evolving into multidrug-resistant forms. As a consequence, there has been a global increase in morbidity and mortality, raising concerns that the world may be approaching a post-antibiotic era (WHO, 2024). Bacterial species such as *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter* spp, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter* spp are of major clinical significance in the current antimicrobial resistance crisis (Kumar et al., 2025). These pathogens, including both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, frequently harbor multidrug resistance (MDR)-associated genes located on genetically complex resistance islands of diverse evolutionary origins. These determinants may be encoded either on chromosomal DNA or carried on mobile genetic elements such as plasmids (Toleman & Walsh, 2011). Antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) in bacteria encode diverse mechanisms that enable survival in the presence of antimicrobial agents, including enzymatic inactivation of drugs, modification of target sites, and active efflux of antibiotics. The spread of these genes is mainly driven by horizontal gene transfer through mobile genetic elements such as plasmids, transposons, and integrons, which promote rapid dissemination within and between bacterial species. In addition, the widespread and often inappropriate use of antibiotics exerts strong selective pressure that accelerates the evolution and global expansion of ARGs across both clinical and environmental ecosystems (Partridge et al., 2018).

Aims of Study

1. To determine the prevalence of urinary tract infections (UTIs) among patients in Al-Rifai District, Thi-Qar province, and to identify the bacterial pathogens responsible for these infections.
2. To evaluate the antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of bacterial isolates causing UTIs and to assess the prevalence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains.
3. To investigate the relationship between urinary tract infections and multidrug-resistant bacteria through the analysis of associated clinical and demographic factors among affected patients.

Materials and Methods

The present study was designed as a case-control investigation conducted on urine samples collected from both male and female patients with a mean age of 34.09 ± 18 years (range: 10–75 years) between July 2022 and January 2023. Participants were recruited from Al-Rifai General Hospital in Thi-Qar province, southern Iraq, through face-to-face interviews. Diagnosis of urinary tract infection (UTI) was based on the presence of pyuria, bacteriuria, and a positive urine culture with bacterial growth $\geq 10^5$ CFU/mL. Midstream urine samples were collected in sterile, screw-capped containers and cultured on blood agar and MacConkey agar using a calibrated loop (0.001 mL) and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Bacterial isolates were identified based on gram staining, conventional biochemical tests, and the VITEK-2 system. Molecular confirmation and detection of bacterial identity and resistance genes were performed using PCR amplification targeting 16S rRNA and specific resistance determinants.

The PCR products were investigated by agarose gel electrophoresis technique as following steps:

1. A one-point five percent agarose gel was prepared using zero-point five X TBE buffer. The mixture was heated in a microwave oven for five minutes until completely dissolved, then allowed to cool to approximately fifty degrees Celsius.
2. Three microliters of ethidium bromide were added to the agarose gel solution.
3. The gel was poured into a casting tray with an appropriately positioned comb and left to solidify for fifteen minutes, after which the comb was carefully removed.
4. The gel tray was placed in the electrophoresis tank and submerged in zero-point five X TBE buffer.
5. Ten microliters of PCR products were loaded into each well, while five microliters of DNA ladder were loaded into the first well. Electrophoresis was performed at 100 volts for one hour.
6. The amplified PCR products were visualized using a UV transilluminator (Addgene, 2025).

Primer sets with their corresponding nucleotide sequences and amplified product sizes of bacteria isolated from urine. The PCR primers for molecular detection of some UTI bacterial based *16S ribosomal RNA* gene and some The resistance genes were designed in this study using NCBI Genbank database and primer 3 plus, these primers were provided by Scientific Reserch Co Ltd in Iraq, as in the following Table 1

Table 1. Polychain Reaction

Primer	Sequence (5'-3')		Product size	Genbank ID number
16S rRNA gene <i>Escherichia coli</i>	F	T CCCC ATCTTT GTCCAT CTC	453 bp	LR7 390 12 1
	R	AG AATACCGG TGACGA ATGC		
16S rRN A gene <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	F	GA GGGTCATTG GAAACT GGA	611 bp	L 375 97 1
	R	TAGC ACGTGT GTAG CCCAAA		
16 S rRNA gene <i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	F	CAG AAGAAGC ACCGGC TAAC	368 bp	LR7 390 04 1
	R	CGGT TTCAAGACCACC AACCT		
16S rRNA gene <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	F	ACCTT GGCGATTGACG TTAC	562 bp	HG 4169 56 1
	R	AAGG GCACCAA TCCATCTC TG		

Table 2. The Nucleotide Sequences of PCR Primers and The Corresponding Amplicon Sizes Used for the Detection of β -Lactam Antibiotic Resistance Genes in Gram-Negative Bacteria

Primers	Sequence (5'-3')		Product size	Genbank ID number
BlaCTX-M	F	C A G A C T G G G T G T G G C A T T G A	241 bp	O M 326 869 1
	R	G C T A A G C T C A G C C A G T G A C A		
blaSHV	F	T A T C G G C C C T C A C T C A A G G A	412 bp	O L 906 381 1
	R	A T C G C T C A T G G T A A T G G C G G		
blaTEM	F	G A G A G T T T T C G C C C C G A A G A	522 bp	O N 221 404 1
	R	A A T A A A C C A G C C A G C C G G A A		
blaAMPC	F	A C A T C T C G C A A C C T A C A C C G	655 bp	L C 4555 76 1
	R	A T A G C T A C C A A A T C C G C C G G		

Table 3. Presents the PCR Primer Sequences and the Expected Amplicon Sizes Used for the Detection of β -Lactam Antibiotic - Resistance Genes in Gram-Positive Bacteria

Primary	Sequence (5'-3')		Product size	Genbank-ID number
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> mecA	F	ACCTCTGCTCAACAAGTTCCA	683-bp	KC243 783 1
	R	ACCACCCAATTTGTCTGCCA		

<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ErmA	F	AGCGGTAAACCCCTCTGAGA	306-bp	KT803896 1
	R	ACAGAGTCTACACTTGGCTTAGG		
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ermC	F	TGGCTCAGGAAAAAGGGCATT	558bp	JF968539 1
	R	TCGTCAATTCCC GCATGTTT		

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 26 and Microsoft Excel 2010 Data were expressed as mean ± standard deviation Normality was assessed using the Kolmogorov– Smirnov test Comparisons between two independent groups were conducted using the independent-samples t-test, while one-way ANOVA was applied for comparisons among three or more groups with normally distributed data. Associations between categorical variables were evaluated using the Chi-square test (Field, 2022).

Results

Bacteria Isolat Ion from Urine

The present study was designed as a case study including (350) samples from urine these samples were collected during the period between July 2022 to January 2023. Males and females, aged (10 to 75) years, with an average age of patients was 34.09 ± 18.67 in Thi-Qar Governorate, southern Iraq in Al-Rifai General Hospital, the results are shown from 350 urine samples, 150 (42.9%), are positive for bacterial growth but 200 (57.1%) samples were Negative for bacterial growth cultural Figure 1 shows Bacterial growth results of the samples include.

Figure 1. Show Bacterial Growth Results of the Samples

Percentages of MDR Bacteria by PCR Analysis of UTI

In the present research, one hundred isolates of multidrug resistant (MDR) bacteria were chosen for subsequent investigation PCR analysis revealed that *Escherichia coli* was the most prevalent uropathogen, accounting for 44 (44%) isolates, followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* with 33 (33%) isolates *Proteus mirabilis* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were identified in 13 (13%) and 10 (10%) isolates, respectively (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Percentage Distribution of Multidrug- Resistant (MDR) Bacteria Identified by PCR in Urinary Tract Infections

Figure 3. Agarose gel electrophoresis of PCR-amplified 16S rRNA gene fragments used for the identification of *Escherichia coli* isolates Lane M represents the DNA marker (100–2000 bp ladder), while lanes 1–21 show positive amplification products corresponding to E coli, with an expected fragment size of 453 bp

Figure 4. Agarose gel electrophoresis analysis of PCR products targeting the 16S rRNA gene for the identification of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates Lane M contains the DNA molecular weight marker (100–2000 bp ladder), whereas lanes 1–16 represent positive S aureus* isolates, showing the expected amplification product of 611 bp

Figure 5. Agarose gel electrophoresis image that showed PCR product analysis of 16S ribosomal RNA gene for detection *Proteus mirabilis* isolates M (Marker ladder 2000-100bp) Lane (1-13) Showed positive Proteus mirabilis isolates 16S ribosomal RNA gene at 368bp product size

Figure 6. Agarose gel electrophoresis image that showed PCR product analysis of 16S ribosomal RNA gene for detection *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates M (Marker ladder 2000-100 bp) Lane (1-10) Showed positive Klebsiella pneumoniae isolates 16S ribosomal RNA gene at 562bp product size

Antibiotic Susceptibility

The Antibiotic susceptibility test was assessed -by automated VITEK-2 compact system using AST-N222 cards. The results showed as in tables 1-4 and represented the Antibiotic susceptibility profile of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella Pneumonia* and *Proteus mirabilis*, indicated that the isolation varied in their susceptibility to the antibiotics.

Table 4. Sensitive Testing of *Staphylococcus aureus* Isolates with Selected Antibiotics

Types of Antibiotics	Interpretation			P
	Resistance	Intermediate	Sensitive	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>				
Benzyl penicillin	33 (100 0%)	0 (0%)	0(0%)	P= 0 001 † HS
Oxacillin	33 (100 0%)	0 (0%)	0(0%)	
Erythromycin	33 (100 0%)	0 (0%)	0(0%)	
Trimethoprim / Sulfamethoxazole	2 (6 1 %)	0 (0%)	31 (93 9%)	
Gentamicin	25(75 7%)	0 (0%)	8 (24 3%)	
Levofloxacin	14 (42 4%)	0 (0%)	19 (57 6%)	
Fusdic acid	30 (90 9%)	0 (0%)	3(9 1%)	
Moxifloxacin	4 (12 1 %)	0 (0%)	29 (87 9%)	
Tobramycin	21 (63 6%)	0 (0%)	12 (36 4%)	
Linezolid	4 (12 1 %)	0 (0%)	29 (87 9%)	
Vancomycin	10 (30 3%)	0 (0%)	23 (69 7%)	
Rifampin	6 (18 2%)	0 (0%)	27 (81 8%)	
Tetracycline	33 (100 0%)	0 (0%)	0(0%)	
Clindamycin	23 (69 7%)	0 (0%)	10 (30 3%)	
Ciprofloxacin	4 (12 1 %)	2 (6 1 %)	27 (81 8%)	
Clarithromycin	33 (100%)	0(0 0 %)	0 (0 0 %)	

Note: *n*: number -of cases; SD: standard deviation; †: independent samples t-test; HS: Highly significant at $P \leq 0.001$

Table 5. Sensitive Testing of *Escherichia coli* Isolates with Selected Antibiotics

Types of Antibiotics	Interpretation			P
	Resistance	Intermediate	Sensitive	
<i>Escherichia coli</i>				
Amoxicillin	44 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	P= 0 001 † HS
Ampicillin	44 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	
Cefazolin	42 (98%)	0 (0%)	2 (2%)	
Cefoxitin	39(95%)	0 (0%)	5 (5%)	
Ceftazidime	2 (2%)	2 (2%)	40(96%)	
Ceftriaxone	36(81 9%)	0 (0%)	8(18 1%)	
Imipenem	0(0%)	2 (2%)	42(98%)	
Gentamicin	10(43 2%)	0 (0%)	34(56 8%)	
Ciprofloxacin	17 (38 6%)	0 (0%)	27 (61 4%)	
Levofloxacin	23 (52 3%)	0 (0%)	21 (47 7%)	
Tigecycline	10 (22 7%)	2 (4 5%)	32 (72 8%)	
Nitrofurantion	4 (72 8%)	0 (0%)	40(27 2%)	
Trimethoprim	38 (86 4%)	0 (0%)	6 (13 6%)	
Erythromycin	44 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	
Clarithromycin	42 (95 5%)	0 (0%)	2(4 5%)	

Note: *n*: number of cases; SD: standard deviation; †: independent samples t-test; HS: Highly significant at $P \leq 0.001$

Table 6. Sensitive Testing of *Klebsiella pneumonia* Isolates with Selected Antibiotics

Types of Antibiotics	Interpretation			P
	Resistance	Intermediate	Sensitive	
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>				
Amoxicillin	10 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	P=0.001 † HS
Ampicillin	10 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	
Cefazolin	10 (100.0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0.0%)	
Cefoxitin	10 (100.0%)	0 (0%)	4 (40.0%)	
Ceftazidime	2(20.0%)	0 (0%)	8 (80.0%)	
Ceftriaxone	10 (100.0%)	0 (0%)	(0.0%)	
Gentamicin	2 (20.0%)	0 (0%)	8 (80.0%)	
Ciprofloxacin	2 (20.0%)	2 (20.0%)	6 (60.0%)	
Levofloxacin	8(80.0%)	0 (0%)	6 (60.0%)	
Tigecycline	2 (20.0%)	0 (0%)	8 (80.0%)	
Nitrofurantion	4 (40%)	0 (0%)	6 (60.0%)	
Trimethoprim/ Sulfa methoxazole	5 (50%)	0 (0%)	5 (50.0%)	
Erythromycin	10 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	
Clarithromycin	10 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	

Note: n: number of cases; SD: standard deviation; †: independent samples t-test; HS: Highly significant at $P \leq 0.001$

Table 7. Sensitive Testing of *Proteus mirabilis* Isolates with Selected Antibiotics

Types of Antibiotics	Interpretation			P
	Resistance	Intermediate	Sensitive	
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>				
Amoxicillin	13 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	P=0.001 † HS
Ampicillin	13 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	
Cefazolin	13 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	
Cefoxitin	13(100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	
Ceftazidime	1 (2.3%)	0 (0%)	12 (97.7%)	
Ceftriaxone	9 (69.2%)	0 (0%)	4 (30.8%)	
Gentamicin	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	13 (100.0%)	
Ciprofloxacin	7 (53.8%)	0 (0%)	6 (46.2%)	
Levofloxacin	7 (53.8%)	0 (0%)	6 (46.2%)	
Tigecycline	9 (69.2%)	0 (0%)	4 (30.8%)	
Nitrofurantion	11 (84.6%)	0 (0%)	2 (15.4%)	
Trimethoprim/ Sulfa methoxazole	9 (69.2%)	0 (0%)	4 (30.8%)	
Erythromycin	13 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	

Note: n: number of cases; SD: standard deviation; †: independent samples t-test; HS: Highly significant at $P \leq 0.001$

Frequency Distribution of Gram Positive and Gran Negative MDR Bacteria According to PCR

Frequency distribution of gram positive and gran negative MDR bacteria according to gram stain was show in (figure 6) The present results showed 33 (33%) of bacterial isolates were gram positive bacteria and 67 (67%) of bacterial isolates are gram negative bacteria

Figure 7. Percentages of MDR Bacterial Isolates of Urinary Tract Infection According to PCR

Molecular detection of Antibiotic resistance genes of *mecA*, *ermA* and *ermC* genes of *S aureus* Specific PCR primers were employed to detect the presence of the *mecA*, *ermA*, and *ermC* genes among *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates. The results demonstrated that all examined isolates (33/33, 100%) carried these resistance genes, as presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Detection of *mecA*, *ermA* and *ermC* genes of *Staph Aureus*

Results	Antibiotic resistance genes		
	<i>mecA</i>	<i>ermA</i>	<i>ermC</i>
	Frequency	Frequency	Frequency
Positive,- n (%)	33, (100 0%)	33, (100 0%)	33, (100 0%)
Negative,- n (%)	0	0	0

Figure 8. Agarose gel electrophoresis image that showed PCR product analysis of beta lactams antibiotics resistance genes in *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates M (Marker ladder 2000-100bp) Lane (1-16) Showed positive *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates for *mecA*, *ermA*, and *ermC* at (683bp, 306, and 558bp PCR product size) respectively

Molecular Detection of Antibiotic Resistance Genes, of *BlaCTX-M*, *BlaSHV*, *BlaTEM* and *BlaAMPC* of Gram Negative Bacterial Species

According to Table 9, PCR analysis demonstrated a high prevalence of β -lactamase genes among Gram-negative bacterial isolates Significant differences were observed in the distribution of *BlaCTX-M*, *BlaSHV*, and *BlaAMPC* genes among *E coli*, *K pneumoniae*, and *P mirabilis* isolates (P = 0 001), while *BlaTEM* was detected in all isolates.

Table 9. Detection of *BlaCTX-M*, *BlaSHV*, *BlaTEM* and *BlaAMPC* Genes in Gram Negative Bacterial Species

Antibiotic resistance Genes	Bacterial species			P
	<i>E coli</i>	<i>K pneumonia</i>	<i>P mirabilis</i>	
BlaCTX-M gene				
Positive, n (%)	36 (81.8%)	10 (100.0%)	4 (30.8%)	0.001 ¥ S
Negative, n (%)	8 (18.2%)	0	9 (69.2%)	
BlaSHV gene				
Positive, n (%)	13 (29.5%)	10 (100.0%)	13 (100.0%)	0.001 ¥ S
Negative, n (%)	31 (70.5%)	0	0	
BlaTEM gene				
Positive, n (%)	44 (100.0)	10 (100.0)	13 (100.0%)	...
Negative, n (%)	0	0	0	
BlaAMPC gene				
Positive, n (%)	40 (90.9%)	10 (100.0%)	4 (30.8%)	0.001 ¥ S
Negative, n (%)	4 (9.1%)	0	9 (69.2%)	

Note: SD: standard deviation; n: number of cases; ¥: chi-square test; S: significant at $p > 0.05$

Figure 9. Agarose gel electrophoresis of PCR-amplified β -lactam antibiotic resistance genes in *Escherichia coli* isolates. Lane M represents the DNA molecular weight marker (100–2000 bp ladder). Lanes 1–19 show positive amplification of one or more resistance genes, including *bla-CTX-M*, *bla-SHV*, *bla-TEM*, and *bla-ampC*, with expected product sizes of 241 bp, 412 bp, 522 bp, and 655 bp, respectively.

Figure 10. Agarose gel electrophoresis showing PCR amplification of β -lactam antibiotic resistance genes in *Proteus mirabilis* isolates. Lane M represents the DNA molecular weight marker (100–2000 bp ladder). Lanes 1–6 display positive amplification of *bla-CTX-M*, *bla-SHV*, *bla-TEM*, and *bla-ampC* genes, with expected product sizes of 241 bp, 412 bp, 522 bp, and 655 bp, respectively.

Figure 11. Agarose gel electrophoresis illustrating PCR amplification of β -Lactam antibiotic resistance genes in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates. Lane M represents the DNA molecular weight marker (100–2000 bp ladder). Lanes 1–5 show positive amplification of *bla-CTX-M*, *bla-SHV*, *bla-TEM*, and *bla-ampC* genes, with expected product sizes of 241 bp, 412 bp, 522 bp, and 655 bp, respectively.

Discussion

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are one of the most prevalent bacterial infections globally. Recently, the emergence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) bacteria carrying antibiotic resistance genes has made treatment more difficult. Therefore, studying the molecular relationship between UTIs and MDR pathogens is essential to understand resistance patterns and improve infection control. In this study, a total of 350 urine samples were analyzed. The results revealed that 150 samples (42.9%) showed positive bacterial growth, whereas 200 samples (57.1%) were culture-negative.

These findings are consistent with previous studies that reported similar positivity rates among urine samples. Study Muqdad, (2022) analyzed 320 urine samples and found that 50 samples (15.6%) showed positive bacterial growth, whereas 270 samples (84.4%) were culture-negative. Similar results were reported in a study conducted in Kirkuk by Shahab et al., (2017), where the proportion of culture-negative samples (77.5%) was higher than that of culture-positive samples (22.5%).

In contrast, the present findings differ from those reported in a study conducted in Lahore, Pakistan (Asmat et al., 2021). In that study, 80 patients with urinary tract infections were investigated, and positive bacterial growth was detected in 65 samples (81.25%), while only 15 samples (18.75%) showed negative bacterial growth.

The similarities and differences between the current study and previous reports may be attributed to variations in geographical location, differences in the recognition and diagnosis of urinary tract infections, screening methods, and associated risk factors. Additionally, environmental conditions and local practices, including socioeconomic status, educational programs, healthcare services, and hygiene practices, may influence the observed prevalence rates.

In this study, a total of 100 multidrug-resistant (MDR) isolates were subjected to further analysis. Based on PCR identification, the distribution of uropathogens causing urinary tract infections (UTIs) was as follows: 44 isolates (44%) were identified as *Escherichia coli*, 33 isolates (33%) as *Staphylococcus aureus*, 13 isolates (13%) as *Proteus mirabilis*, and 10 isolates (10%) as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

These findings are consistent with the results reported by Simon-Oke et al., (2019) in Akure, Nigeria, where *E. coli* accounted for 20 isolates (32.8%) among 61 culture-positive UTI samples, while *S. aureus* accounted for 9 isolates (14.8%). Similar observations were reported by Jain et al., (2015), who found that *E. coli* was the most common bacterial isolate (44.2%), followed by *S. aureus* (21.1%) among patients with UTIs. Likewise, study Muqdad, (2022) reported *E. coli* as the predominant pathogen (36%), followed by *S. aureus* (24%). Comparable results were also obtained by Souad, (2022), who recorded *E. coli* in 55.0% of cases and *S. aureus* in 37.5% of cases.

The predominance of *E. coli* in UTIs can be explained by its presence as a normal component of the intestinal microbiota. Infection commonly occurs through contamination originating from the rectal area, either via poor hand hygiene or due to the anatomical proximity of the urethra and vaginal opening to the anus, particularly in females. This facilitates the migration of *E. coli* into the urinary tract and bladder, leading to cystitis. If the infection ascends to the kidneys, it may result in acute pyelonephritis. Furthermore, *E. coli* possesses numerous virulence factors, including adhesins and extracellular enzymes, which enhance its ability to colonize host tissues and evade mechanical defense mechanisms. These characteristics increase its pathogenic potential, contributing to severe infections and inflammatory responses that may play a role in disease progression (Abass et al., 2018).

Antibiotic resistance is becoming a global public health issue due to the increased morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs attributed to resistant bacteria. Antibiotic-resistant bacteria have become a serious threat at the global level more than 700,000 deaths are caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria each year and it is estimated that the number of deaths could grow to 10 million deaths per year in 2050 (CDC, 2019). The present study showed the highest resistance among *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates included in

this study was against Benzyl penicillin (100%), followed by oxacillin (100%), Erythromycin (100 %), Fusidic acid (90.9%) Gentamicin (75.7%) the current result is agree with the study in the northwestern region of Ethiopia by Belete, (2020) which showed that Gram-positive bacteria represented 31 (62%) of the total bacteria isolated 50 and the results showed that the antibiotic benzyl penicillin was (100%) also agree with Simon-Oke et al., (2019) in Nigeria showed that the antibiotic resistance benzyl penicillin was (100%), Erythromycin (100%) and agree with Muqdad, (2022), who showed that Benzyl penicillin (100%) followed by oxacillin (100%), Erythromycin (88.8%), the *mecA* gene in *Staphylococcus aureus* is the one responsible for resistance to β -lactams the product of *mecA* is the peptidoglycan synthesis enzyme, penicillin-binding protein (PBP2a) involved in cross-linking of peptidoglycan in the bacterial cell wall. In this study (100%) of *S aureus* strains produced beta-lactamase it is known that the production of beta-lactamase is a major resistance mechanism that *Staphylococcus aureus* uses to prevent the action of oxacillin and Benzyl penicillin antimicrobial susceptibility testing of Gram-negative bacteria was conducted against commonly used antibiotics to determine their resistance profiles the present results indicated that the isolations were *E coli* strains 44 resistant to multiple antibiotics, including ampicillin(100%) In addition to (100%) of *K pneumonia* and *Proteus mirabilis* were resistance to ampicillin and other beta-lactamase antibiotic the current study agrees with the finding in Lahore, Pakistan, by Asmat et al., (2021), who showed that the rate of Gram-negative bacteria was 57 (87.7%) of the total sample, which was 65 bacterial growth cultures in the urinary tract, and the results were that bacteria resistant to amoxicillin (100%), followed by ampicillin (95.3%) and the result agrees with study by Bahati et al., (2020) in southwestern Uganda, where its results showed Amoxicillin (95.7%), and Ampicillin (95%) Gram-negative bacteria that are resistant to beta-lactamase antibiotic because they have them the phenotypic expression of ESBLs is controlled by specific mutations in certain genes such as blaTEM, blaSHV, and blaCTX-M The mutations alter the amino acid configuration of the encoded proteins, thus conferring the ESBLs with the ability to hydrolyze a wider spectrum of β -lactam antibiotics, including penicillin and cephalosporins (Jena et al., 2017).

The present results showed 33 (33%) of bacterial isolates were gram positive bacteria and 67 (67%) of bacterial isolates are gram negative bacteria this result agree with study by Asmat et al., (2021) in Lahore, Pakistan that presented the rate of gram negative bacteria was 57 (87.7%) of the total sample which were 65 bacterial growth culture in urinary tract infection and the gram positive bacteria was 8 (12.3%) of the total sample which were 65 bacterial growth culture and this result agree with study in Kirkuk province of Iraq by Shahab et al., (2017), who recorded bacterial growth in urine specimens was 40(38.09%) specimens positive bacterial culture, 9(22.5%) were gram positive bacteria, while 31(77.5%) specimens were Gram and this study disagreed with study by Bahati et al., (2020). in South-western Uganda, that shows that the total rate of urine samples collected from urinary tract infection was 400 which showed the rate of gram negative bacteria was 20 (39.2%) of the total sample which were 51 bacterial growth culture in urinary tract infection and the gram positive bacteria was 31 (60.8%) of the total sample which were 51 bacterial growth culture, and this study disagree with the results of the Iraqi governorate of Karbala, which were conducted by the researchers Al-Wazni & Hadi, (2015), that showed that the percentage of Gram-negative bacteria was 9 (18%) out of the total sample, which was 50 farms bacterial growth in urinary tract infection gram-positive bacteria were 41 (82%) of the total sample of 50 bacterial growth cultures in urinary tract infection. The reason for this alteration between the current study and other studies may be due to Geographic differences, differences in UTI recognition, screening methods, confounding risk factors, and a variety of environmental conditions and practices, such as social and economic norms, educational initiatives, and health care policies (Tadesse et al., 2018).

The present study demonstrated that all three resistance genes (*mecA*, *ermA*, and *ermC*) were detected in all *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates (33/33, 100%) These findings are consistent with a previous report Alghizzi et al., (2021), which documented approximately 93.3% of *mecA*-positive isolates Similarly, a study conducted in Jordan Al-Dmour et al., (2023) reported that all MRSA isolates (100%) harbored the *mecA*

gene and showed complete resistance to multiple β -lactam antibiotics, including oxacillin, ceftazidime, ceftiofur, ceftazidime, cefoxitin, aztreonam, and ampicillin. The *mecA* gene encodes the penicillin-binding protein PBP2a, which has low affinity for β -lactam antibiotics, thereby conferring resistance to methicillin and related drugs. This mechanism also results in cross-resistance within the β -lactam class, making treatment of such infections more challenging (Grazul et al., 2023).

In the current study, *ermA* and *ermC* genes were also detected in all *S. aureus* isolates (100%). This is in agreement with previous studies Idrees et al., (2023) & Quezada-Aguiluz et al., (2022), which reported high levels of resistance among MRSA isolates to macrolide antibiotics such as erythromycin and azithromycin. Specifically, MRSA isolates showed resistance rates of 97% to erythromycin and azithromycin (Quezada-Aguiluz et al., 2022), while *ermA* was detected in 88% of MRSA isolates in the same study.

The emergence and spread of antibiotic resistance in developing countries have been attributed to several factors, including poor regulation of antimicrobial use, inadequate surveillance systems, inappropriate prescription practices, and insufficient quality control of antibiotics. Easy access to antibiotics without strict regulation further contributes to misuse and overuse, often driven by limited awareness of antimicrobial resistance. Collectively, these factors significantly promote the development and spread of resistant bacterial strains (Chokshi et al., 2019).

The present results are in agreement with a study conducted in China (Shi et al., 2015), which reported a high prevalence of *bla*CTX-M among ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* isolates recovered from multiple hospitals across different cities. In that study, 130 *E. coli* isolates were analyzed, of which 126 (96.9%) carried the *bla*CTX-M gene. Similarly, a study from Jordan (Al-Sheboul et al., 2023) reported that among 99 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates obtained from various clinical samples in three major hospitals, ESBL genes were highly prevalent, with *bla*SHV detected in 100% of isolates and *bla*CTX-M in 85.7%, while only four isolates were negative for CTX-M-type genes. In addition, findings from Tanzania (Mwakyoma et al., 2023) showed that 98.9% of *E. coli* isolates harbored ESBL genes, including *bla*CTX-M, *bla*TEM, or *bla*SHV, with only 1.1% lacking these determinants. Another study (Enogiomwan & Ibeh, 2018) also reported a high occurrence of *bla*ampC (80%) among clinical isolates. However, the present findings are not consistent with a study conducted in Benin City, Nigeria (Enogiomwan & Ibeh, 2018), which reported a lower prevalence of CTX-M-positive uropathogenic *E. coli* (29.7%) among 350 samples.

Conclusion

In this study concluded that the result of this research showed that there is strong relationship between multidrug-resistant bacteria and urinary tract infections.

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